

NOTES

Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) Complexes of 3-(*o*-Carboxyphenyl)-1-Methyl Triazene-1-Oxide

R. L. DUTTA* and RAMADHAR SHARMA**

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan,
Burdwan-713 104

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MAJUMDAR and coworkers^{1,2} synthesised dibasic tridentate 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-phenyl/methyl triazene-1-oxides(I) and studied their complexes with transition metal ions^{3,4}. We wish to report the complexes of 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene-1-oxide (TH₂) with zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II).

Experimental

The ligand was prepared following published procedure².

Zinc(II) chelate [ZnT]: A hot solution of zinc(II) acetate (0.01 mole) in 15 ml dehydrated alcohol was added to a hot 20 ml aqueous-alcoholic solution of 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-1-methyl triazene-1-oxide (0.01 mole). Just on mixing and swirling white crystals began to separate out. The product was filtered, washed thoroughly with acetone and dried over silica gel.

Cadmium(II) chelate [CdT]: A hot aqueous solution of cadmium(II) acetate (0.01 mole) in 10 ml water was added to a hot 20 ml aqueous-alcoholic solution of the ligand (0.01 mole). A colourless crystalline complex separated out which was treated as described above.

Mercury(II) chelate [HgT]: Mercury(II) chelate was prepared following the method adopted for [ZnT]. 1-2 drops of glacial acetic acid were added to the alcoholic solution of mercury(II) acetate to make the solution clear.

Zinc(II) mixed chelate with *o*-phenanthroline [ZnT. *o*-phen]: Mono(ligand) zinc(II) chelate was suspended in hot methanol and a methanolic solution of *o*-phenanthroline in 1:1 molar ratio was added to it. The colour of the chelate crystals immediately changed from white to yellow. The mixture was refluxed for half an hour, the needle-shaped yellow crystals filtered, washed with methanol and dried over silica gel.

Cadmium(II) mixed chelate with *o*-phenanthroline [CdT. *o*-phen]: Mono(ligand) cadmium(II) chelate and *o*-phenanthroline in methanol (1:1 molar ratio) reacted to give a clear solution. The solution was refluxed for half an hour and allowed to stand. After a few days, the resulting viscous mass became granular on scratching with acetone. The product was filtered and dried over silica gel.

Analyses and physical measurements: Zinc and cadmium were determined as oxides^{1,4} and mercury as sulphide^{1,5}. Nitrogen was estimated by using the method of Dumas. C, H analyses as well as IR spectra were done at C. D. R. I., Lucknow.

Results and Discussion

Insolubility of these complexes did not allow conductivity and molecular weight determinations. The analytical data (Table 1) support [MT] and [MT.*o*-phen] stoichiometries. The analytical and infrared data (Table 1) of mono(ligand) metal(II) chelates indicate an apparent coordination number of three. While there is evidence for only two three-coordinate zinc(II) complexes⁵, there is not a single example for three-coordinate cadmium(II) complex. Mercury(II) has been found to give quite a few three-coordinate complexes⁶. The three-coordinate zinc(II) complex, [Zn(SiNMe₃)₂Py], is a typical example where steric hindrance plays a major role in limiting the coordination number to three for elements which normally favour higher coordination numbers. Three coordinate mercury(II) results from the steric requirements of the ligands. Examination of models clearly indicates that the present ligand does not fulfill conditions for giving three-coordinate complexes. The extreme insolubility of [MT] chelates in common organic solvents suggests a polymeric structure [MT]_n. It is believed that the metal(II) ions acquire their usual four coordination through polymerisation. Since zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) (d¹⁰ systems) have no CFSE, their coordination numbers and stereochemistries are determined by the ionic size, electrostatic and covalent bonding forces⁷. Polymerisation of [MT] chelates is possible either through $\overset{1}{N} \rightarrow O$ oxygen or

** Present address: Department of Chemistry, R. D. & D. J. College, Monghyr-811 201 (Bihar), under Bhagalpur University.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND INFRARED DATA (cm⁻¹) OF TH_n, [MT] AND [MT.o-phen]

Compound	m.p. (°C)	%M	%N	%C	%H	ν_{N-H}	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{N\rightarrow O}$	ν_{o-phen}
TH _n	—	—	—	—	—	~3210s	~1680s	~1300m	—
ZnT (Colourless)	<250	25.55 (25.31)*	16.43 (16.25)	37.34 (37.15)	3.01 (2.70)	—	~1610s	~1235s	—
CdT (Colourless)	186-87	36.37 (36.81)	14.08 (13.75)	31.61 (31.44)	2.69 (2.29)	—	~1612s	~1235s	—
HgT (Yellow)	175-76	49.87 (50.10)	10.87 (10.67)	24.71 (24.39)	2.03 (1.78)	—	~1610s	~1938s	—
ZnT.o-phen (Yellow)	246-47	15.24 (14.97)	10.06 (10.13)	54.43 (54.71)	3.62 (3.40)	—	~1610s ~1238s	~730s	1170m
CdT.o-phen (Colourless)	165	22.79 (23.15)	14.31 (14.42)	49.65 (49.43)	3.32 (3.10)	—	~1610s ~1238s	~730s	1170m 1420m

s=strong, m=medium, * Figures in parentheses indicate calculated values.

C=O oxygen of the COO⁻ group. Bhattacharyya and Ray⁵ have argued in favour of C=O oxygen of the COO⁻ group acting as bridging atom in [CuT]_n chelate based on some X-ray crystallographic studies in similar type of complexes. Since the [CuT]_n, [ZnT]_n, [CdT]_n and [HgT]_n have same stoichiometry as well as very similar ir spectra it is believed that the C=O oxygen of COO⁻ group acts as a bridging atom. Also bridging through N¹→O oxygen will lead to a strained four membered ring while bridging through C=O oxygen will offer a strain free eight membered ring involving the two metal ions. Four membered rings have been found to be highly strained in tetrahedral geometry⁹ and is also likely to lead to subnormal magnetic moment in [CuT]_n through super exchange. [CuT]_n, however, shows a normal magnetic moment³ of 1.85 B.M.

The ν_{N-H} band of the ligand at ~3210 cm⁻¹ disappears and $\nu_{C=O}$ at ~1680 cm⁻¹ is lowered considerably to ~1610 cm⁻¹ in metal complexes (Table 1). $\nu_{N\rightarrow O}$ at ~1300 cm⁻¹ is also lowered to ~1235 cm⁻¹ indicating coordination through N¹→O→M¹⁰. Zinc(II) and cadmium(II) mono-(ligand) complexes provide mixed chelates with o-phenanthroline while mono(ligand) mercury(II) chelate does not do so. Such failure of mono-(ligand) mercury(II) chelate to raise its coordination number is in tune with our earlier observations^{11,12} with monobasic bidentate and monobasic tridentate triazene-1-oxides. [ZnT.o-phen]_n, [CdT.o-phen]_n and [CuT.o-phen]_n mixed chelates have been identified by the appearance of new characteristic ir bands at ~730, ~1170 and ~1420 cm⁻¹ for coordinated o-phenanthroline^{10,11}, disappearance of ν_{N-H} , lowering of $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{N\rightarrow O}$ bands. These mixed chelates are also insoluble in common organic solvents. A polymeric structure (cf. Fig. 1, reference 13) appears consistent with all properties¹².

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Cobalt(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with Substituted Aminobenzothiazoles, Part-II

RAJENDRA P. MISRA*, BIPIN B. MAHAPATRA
and
S. GURU**

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3
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In a recent work¹, we reported the synthesis of a series of Hg(II) complexes with substituted aminobenzothiazoles. As an extension of the previous report, the present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of Co(II) and Cu(II) complexes with monodentate 2-amino-6-methyl benzothiazole and 2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole.

** All correspondence to this author.